

E- GIFTING A VALUABLE ASSET IN A SINGLE CLICK

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Abstract

From tiny tots to old people, gifts have always excited humans which is why choosing a right and meaningful gift always requires time and effort. Gifts have a significant value as the giver will be able to resonate the emotional feelings of the receiver. Though the giver is satisfied with a smile on the receiver's face, the receiver gets fretted about the value it possesses in the long term. The contemporaries of India as in the developed economies like UK, U.S.A are some of the countries which spend enormous amounts on gifting considering that gifts tend to strengthen relationships between people. It is disapproved by science that gifts are meant to be a "surprise", yet to ask an individual on what they want to be gifted is a taboo. Gifts should always be what the receiver needs and is unique to an individual. When gifts are desired so much, have we ever wondered if we could gift ownership of an enterprise or an asset that is futuristic and fetch returns once held for a period of time? In an unprecedented pandemic where socializing is virtual, can shares/bonds/mutual funds be gifted electronically in a single click? Zerodha broking limited, an indian financial services company and also India's biggest stock broking firm has come up with a pensive way of gifting i.e online gifting shares through seamless process. We are in a thought-provoking juncture wherein this initiative by Zerodha cultivates the trading habits in individuals. In a country where investing in share markets is trending and considered the nation's future, does this step by Zerodha help the economy financially literate and an individual to be financially healthy? This study aims to build awareness amongst the common public about online gifting of shares. It also highlights the pros and cons involved in online gifting of shares, bonds or mutual funds and also a comparison of online and offline gifting with a brief on its tax implications.

Keywords: Gifting of shares, Zerodha, Online, Financial Literacy

INTRODUCTION

All of us have at some point in our life either received gifts or presented gifts, but how many such gifts have changed the future or brought in prospects to the receiver. We all are much aware about what is a share and how it works, just for understanding A share is part of company's capital which is been sold to the general public Via IPO (Initial Public Offering) and later the same shares are sold in secondary market by listing them stock exchanges like NSE and BSE. These shares are bought and sold in big volume on a daily basis by many people in the name of stock traders. After the use of BOLT in BSE, buying and selling of shares became much easier by buying them electronically and holding them in the form of a Dematerialized (DEMAT) account. With the advent in technology, there was a rapid growth in the usage of smartphones which later paved the way for many apps to be user-friendly and handy even for trading of shares. Recently, youth have kick started their investment in the share market by installing these applications onto their smartphones. The present study throws a spotlight on how shares can be gifted to near and dear ones effortlessly in a single click and

the procedure involved by also touching upon the pros and cons of gifting E shares in a couple of minutes.

OBJECTIVES

- To understand the concept of e-gifting of shares
- To depict the process involved in gifting of shares
- Comparison of offline Gifting and online gifting of shares
- Enlighten on pros and cons of E- Gifting of shares

NEED

Gifting is alluring and has always been a surprise for humans. Pandemic has an augmented platform for virtual gifting, where People are spending a humongous amount in gifts that are foreseen to be depreciable. This study emphasizes on gifting of shares of a company whose value might appreciate in the near future. At present, internet penetration has made this idea of gifting shares feasible and much simpler.

In the past the shares were only given to employees as an option called ESOP, which is even now very famous. For e.g. Fresh works gifting has also been through offline mode which was tedious back then. Zerodha has taken this to the next level by gifting the securities to our most valued and loved person. Shares and nominee

Recently TTD started their Demat account where devotees can transfer or donate shares to the trust and many big corporations like Wipro and TATA are doing the same with regard to CSR activities.

With all this in one hand the unicorn startup Zerodha has launched this new system where we can give shares to others in a very simple process. The need for this study is what is E - Gifting of shares, Procedures and tax implication for the same as been analysed.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is based on secondary data. The facts and data for this study has been collected from various editorials, websites and research articles.

PROCEDURE

For Sender:

- Sender is required to update the name, mobile number and email address of the receiver
- Stocks, ETF or gold bonds can be gifted only if the sender holds them in his demat account and only if it's included in an approved list of securities. T1 holdings* cannot be gifted.
*T1 Holdings - generally Indian stock exchanges follow Rolling settlement method, where the traded securities are settled on succeeding dates. In India, Equity settlement time is T+2 days. For eg. Shares purchased on Tuesday will be settled by Thursday evening.

- Once the sender transfers his gift, the application requires acceptance from the receiver's (who should mandatorily hold an account with Zerodha) end within 7 days failing which the transaction gets cancelled automatically
- Upon acceptance by recipient, the sender will be notified with SMS and email requesting to approve the recipient's detail and also the shares to be transferred using CDSL TPIN (Central Depository Services Limited Transaction Personal Identification Number) earlier POA was required to transact/trade
- Right after approving shares to be debited, Zerodha sets up off-market gift transactions on trading days at 5PM which has to be verified through OTP generation of which requires PAN/16-digit DP ID. The timeline to verify OTP is 8PM the same day. gifted shares get reflected in the recipient's account the next day and added to their holdings.
- Charged applied is nil for gifting and for off-market transfer, higher of Rs.25 or 0.03% per scrip will be charged
- Calculation of P&L/buy averages - stock's closing price on date of transfer will be considered
- In case the stocks are gifted and at the same time sold in market then it will result in an auction penalty

For Recipient:

- SMS and email notification reaches the receiver mentioning the name of the sender
- Gift can be claimed only if he/she holds an account with Zerodha
- The procedure is simple that the receiver just has to follow the link and accept the gift sent
- Sender can cancel any time before the transfer actually takes place

COMPARISON (Offline vs Online)

Offline / transfer through demat form - According to the notification received from SEBI after 1st April, 2019, shares can be gifted or transferred only when they are in DEMAT form and not when held in physical form.

Since the shares are transferred as a gift, they are without consideration hence off market mechanism is followed when shares are gifted offline. Procedure followed for gifting of shares through offline medium is tedious as the donor initially has to fill in Delivery Instruction Slip (DIS) and submit it to the Depository Participant (DP). It is mandatory to fill in DP ID, name, Donee's client ID and Name, ISIN and the total number of shares to be transferred along with the execution date. This acts like an instruction to the Depository Participant.

Receipt Instruction: Receipt instruction is filled out by the donee and submitted to his depository participant. Post which, the shares that are received from the donor's depository participant will be credited to donee's depository participant account. Receipt instruction also requires DP ID, name, etc.

The duplicate copy of DIS or the receipt instruction is given to the respective parties once the required forms are received. Actual transfer of shares as gift will be executed on the date mentioned in the DIS. It is advisable to have a gift deed on stamp paper as it will act as legal proof. Shares once gifted are irrevocable.

Online:

Online gifting of shares is now hassle free in just a click by Zerodha for which the charge is 0.03% of gift value or Rs.25 whichever is higher. All that the donor and done needs is just to have a demat account with Zerodha.

TAX IMPLICATION

Gifting involves a sender and a receiver. From the sender's perspective, there is no liability to pay taxes after the abolition of Gift Tax Act (GTA). At the receiver's end, it is taxable and has to be reported under "Income from Other Sources" under section 56(2) of Income tax Act. The condition on which tax is imposed on the recipient is while gifting movable property like in our case "Shares or Mutual Funds", if there is no consideration and the fair market value exceeds INR 50,000. There are few situations that exempt recipients from paying tax for gifting - when the gift is received from a relative, when it's on an occasion of marriage and when it's through will or by way of family inheritance.

CHALLENGES

- Adequate Financial Literacy on trading or dealing with shares plays a crucial role
- Parties involved in gifting should have an account with "Zerodha"
- Account holders of any other financial institution might not be able to avail such advantage from Zerodha
- Advent knowledge on trading is a prerequisite for gifting of shares as its about the value that is being transferred

SUGGESTIONS

- An Awareness program can be organised by the regulatory body SEBI and as well as by the NSE and BSE
- This could create a new market where it can motivate the young investors to gift a financial valuable asset
- A bit of this can also be marketed in various field so it might attract more towards trading of shares which is in return a very good move for economy as well as the company
- For the Listed Companies this could be a positive move as it will move up their goodwill.
- Other renowned financial institutions like ICICI and HDFC Banks can bring in this initiative for a better reach amongst the common public

CONCLUSION

India's online gifting market is experiencing a boom as there is a demand for personalized gifting. In this stage it is highly important that people are aware of such an option of gifting of shares which has a lot of ease at single click. Though gifting has challenges like having an account opened and charges to be borne, still this form of gifting can be spread across so that people can not only invest prudently but also be prudent gifters. Gifting of shares inculcates the habit of investment at the recipient's end and also brings in awareness about the online platforms or applications available even for small sized investors.

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